

ADDITIONAL EFFECTS OF KINESIO-TAPING ALONG WITH CONSERVATIVE PHYSICAL THERAPY ON UPPER LIMB FUNCTION, RANGE OF MOTION, AND SPASTICITY IN PATIENTS WITH SUBACUTE STROKE

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ABSTRACT

Background and objective: According to the WHO, stroke is a condition characterized by rapidly developing clinical signs of focal (or global) disruption of cerebral function, lasting more than 24 hours or resulting in death, with no apparent cause other than vascular origin. Therefore, the study aimed to assess the additional effects of Kinesio-taping combined with conservative physical therapy on upper limb spasticity, range of motion, and function in patients with subacute stroke.

Methodology:

The study was a one-year (Dec 2023-Dec 2024) randomized controlled trial conducted at Leading Edge Physical Therapy and Rehabilitation in Islamabad on stroke patients. The sampling technique used was a convenience sampling method. Sample size was obtained through G-Power software, which was found to be 40. Out of which 4 were the dropouts, so a study was conducted on 36 patients aged 40-60 years with 1, 1+, and 2 MAS scores and were divided into two groups through the coin toss method of randomization. Data collection tools used for Elbow and wrist range of motion (ROM) were a goniometer, spasticity was assessed via the Modified Ashworth Scale, and upper limb motor function was evaluated using the Wolf Motor Function Test. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21. This clinical trial registry allotted for this study was NCT06674057.

Results: The results of the study included demographics such as the mean \pm SD for age of the participants was 48.89 ± 6.861 , most of the participants were males, 19 (52.78%), and 17 (47.22%) were females. Normality of data was checked through the Shapiro-Wilk test. The data for ROM was normally distributed, while for MAS Score and WMFT, it was non-normally distributed. For within-group analysis Friedman Test was used for ROM, MAS score, and WMT. And, for between-group analyses, Mann Mann-Whitney U test was used for ROM, MAS score, and WMT. Results showed that within-group analysis for ROM, MAS Score, and Wolf Motor function test for both groups showed significant improvement (p -value <0.05), while between the conventional physical therapy and Kinesio taping group for ROM and Wolf Motor assessment test for upper limb function

showed no significant improvement ($p\text{-value}>0.05$) while there was significant improvement in MAS score ($p\text{-value}<0.05$).

Conclusion: This study demonstrated that while both conventional physiotherapy and Kinesio Taping (KT) combined with physiotherapy led to significant improvements in upper limb function, range of motion (ROM), and spasticity in post-stroke patients, although no statistically significant differences were observed between groups in ROM or functional task performance (WMT), yet Kinesio-Taping does offer a greater advantage than conventional physical treatment alone in improving spasticity.

Keywords: kinesiotaping, subacute stroke, spasticity, upper limb function

INTRODUCTION

Stroke is defined by the World Health Organization as a rapidly developed clinical sign of focal (or global) disturbance of cerebral function, lasting more than 24 hours or leading to death, with no apparent cause other than vascular origin (1). Complementing this, the American Heart Association/American Stroke Association categorises stroke to include silent infarctions and haemorrhages affecting the brain, spinal cord, and retina, resulting from vascular injury (2). Globally, stroke is a leading cause of mortality and long-term disability, ranking as the second most common cause of death worldwide (3).

The etiology of stroke is multifactorial, arising from a complex interplay of disease mechanisms and pathophysiological processes. Risk factors are broadly classified as modifiable (e.g., hypertension, smoking, poor diet, physical inactivity) and non-modifiable (e.g., age, sex, ethnicity), with emerging evidence for the roles of inflammation, infections, environmental pollution, and cardiac disorders such as atrial fibrillation (4). Ischemic strokes, accounting for approximately 85% of cases, are primarily caused by large artery atherosclerotic embolism, small vessel arteriolosclerosis, or cardioembolism. The remaining 15% are hemorrhagic strokes, which may occur in deep brain structures like the basal ganglia, the cerebellum, and the brainstem, or in lobar regions (5). Clinical presentation is often sudden and can include unilateral weakness or numbness in the face, arm, or leg; speech difficulties such as dysarthria (slurred speech) or dysphasia (impaired language comprehension or production); non-orthostatic vertigo; headache; ataxia; visual field defects; and abnormal eye movements (6). Prompt diagnosis is critical to mitigate serious consequences. Initial assessment typically involves a non-contrast computed tomography (CT) scan, often followed by advanced imaging like CT angiography and CT perfusion to identify vascular occlusions or perfusion deficits. While diffusion-weighted magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is highly sensitive for detecting early ischemic

changes, its availability in emergency settings is often limited (7).

Management strategies are contingent on factors such as stroke subtype, lesion size, and the affected artery. Current standard care for acute ischemic stroke includes medical management with intravenous thrombolysis (e.g., tPA) and endovascular thrombectomy, both of which significantly improve patient outcomes when applied appropriately (8, 9). Subsequently, rehabilitation is paramount for recovery. Conventional physical therapy, an important element of non-pharmacological management, aims to help patients regain functional capacity through exercises to improve strength, coordination, balance, and mobility, often using assistive devices (10).

Despite its established benefits, conventional physical therapy may be enhanced by adjunctive techniques. Kinesio Taping (KT) is one such modality. KT involves the application of an elastic therapeutic tape designed to provide support and facilitate physiological processes without restricting the range of motion. Proposed mechanisms of action include enhancing lymphatic flow, reducing pain, providing muscular support, and improving proprioception by inhibiting or facilitating neuromuscular function (11, 12).

Emerging research suggests that KT may be a valuable adjunct to conventional stroke rehabilitation. Studies have demonstrated its potential in reducing post-stroke shoulder pain (13) and improving balance and ankle control (14). Furthermore, research by Mota et al. indicated that the use of functional bandages alongside traditional physical therapy promoted motor development in stroke survivors (15). However, the evidence regarding its effects on spasticity reduction and range of motion (ROM) enhancement remains limited and not well-established.

Therefore, this study aims to evaluate the efficacy of integrating Kinesio Taping with standard physiotherapy to accelerate recovery and enhance functional outcomes in patients with subacute stroke. Specifically, it will investigate whether the combined intervention leads to greater improvements in upper

limb function, reduction in spasticity, and enhanced ROM compared to conventional physiotherapy alone. The findings may provide valuable evidence to support the integration of KT into routine rehabilitation protocols, potentially offering new strategies to improve functional outcomes and quality of life for stroke survivors.

Methodology:

This study was a randomized controlled trial conducted over a one-year period from December 2023 to December 2024 at the Leading Edge Physical Therapy and Rehabilitation Centre in Islamabad. A convenience sampling method was used to recruit participants, and the sample size was determined a priori using the G*Power software. From an initial pool of 40 patients, 4 dropped out, resulting in a final sample of 36 individuals aged between 40 and 60 years who exhibited upper limb spasticity with Modified Ashworth Scale (MAS) scores of 1, 1+, or 2. Participants were excluded if they had any congenital deformities, cognitive deficits, a history of fractures or upper limb surgery, or an inability to participate fully. Eligible participants were randomly assigned to one of two groups using a coin toss method: a control group (n = 18) that received conventional physical therapy and an intervention group (n = 18) that received conventional physical therapy combined with Kinesio Taping (KT) applied to the forearm and arm.

All participants underwent treatment three times per week on alternate days for six weeks. The control group's protocol for weeks 1-3 consisted of active-assisted and active range of motion (ROM) exercises (25 repetitions), PNF stretching using the hold-relax technique for targeted muscles (20 repetitions with a 10-second hold), and D1 flexion and extension

patterns (20 repetitions). From weeks 3-6, this regimen was continued with the addition of resistance training using medium-resistance bands. The intervention group received the identical conventional therapy program throughout the six weeks but with the addition of Kinesio Taping applied to the biceps brachii, brachialis, and brachioradialis muscles with a 15% stretch from insertion to origin to reduce spasticity.

The primary outcome measures were elbow and wrist ROM, measured with a goniometer; spasticity, assessed via the Modified Ashworth Scale; and upper limb motor function, evaluated using the Wolf Motor Function Test. After obtaining informed consent, patients were assessed and treated either at the clinic or at home. Participants in the KT group were first screened for skin sensitivity. Baseline assessments were conducted before treatment commenced, with follow-up evaluations performed at 3 and 6 weeks. Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 21. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic data. The Shapiro-Wilk test assessed data normality, and due to the ordinal nature of some scales, non-parametric tests were employed: the Mann-Whitney U test for between-group analysis and the Friedman test for within-group analysis across the three time points.

Results

The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to assess the normality of the data distribution. As detailed in Table 1, all range of motion (ROM) variables were found to be normally distributed ($p > 0.05$). In contrast, the Modified Ashworth Scale (MAS) and all Wolf Motor Function Test (WMT) task scores were non-normally distributed ($p \leq 0.05$), necessitating the use of non-parametric statistical tests for subsequent analysis.

Table 1: Normality of Data Distribution (Shapiro-Wilk Test)

Variable	p-value	Distribution
ROM Forearm Flexion	0.07	Normal
ROM Forearm Supination	0.50	Normal
ROM Wrist Flexion	0.06	Normal
ROM Elbow Flexion	0.10	Normal
MAS Score	0.00	Non-Normal

WMT: Forearm to Table	0.00	Non-Normal
WMT: Forearm to Box	0.00	Non-Normal
WMT: Extend Elbow (Side)	0.00	Non-Normal
WMT: Extend Elbow (Weight)	0.00	Non-Normal
WMT: Hand to Table	0.00	Non-Normal
WMT: Hand to Box	0.00	Non-Normal

Note: $p > 0.05$ indicates normal distribution.

The mean age of the 36 participants was 48.89 years (± 6.8 SD), indicating a middle-aged cohort (Table 2). A Friedman test revealed statistically significant improvements ($p < 0.01$) from baseline to the 6-week follow-up in both the conventional physiotherapy (CP) group and the group receiving CP plus Kinesio Taping (KT) for all outcome measures (Table 3).

For ROM parameters (forearm flexion, forearm supination, elbow flexion, wrist flexion), both groups showed progressive and significant increases in mean scores across the three assessment points. Although both groups improved, the KT group consistently

achieved marginally higher mean ROM values at the final (3rd) assessment.

A similar pattern was observed in functional tasks measured by the WMT. All tasks (i.e., forearm to table, forearm to box, elbow extension (side and weight), hand to table, and hand to box) showed significant within-group improvements over time ($p < 0.01$) for both interventions.

Most notably, spasticity, as measured by the MAS, decreased significantly in both groups ($p < 0.05$). The reduction in mean MAS scores was more pronounced in the KT group (from 1.7 ± 0.5 to 0.6 ± 0.5) compared to the CP group (from 2.1 ± 0.7 to 1.8 ± 0.7).

Table 3: Within-Group Changes Over Time (Friedman Test)

Outcome Measure	Group	Assessment 1 (Mean \pm SD)	Assessment 2 (Mean \pm SD)	Assessment 3 (Mean \pm SD)	p-value
ROM: Forearm Flexion	CP	81.44 \pm 13.18	86.50 \pm 14.06	90.83 \pm 15.36	<0.01
	CP + KT	80.28 \pm 15.42	88.50 \pm 15.62	94.33 \pm 16.08	<0.01
ROM: Elbow Flexion	CP	81.89 \pm 11.30	84.67 \pm 10.95	88.56 \pm 11.01	<0.01
	CP + KT	78.17 \pm 8.69	82.83 \pm 9.49	87.33 \pm 9.04	<0.01
MAS Score	CP	2.1 \pm 0.7	2.1 \pm 0.7	1.8 \pm 0.7	0.01
	CP + KT	1.7 \pm 0.5	1.2 \pm 0.4	0.6 \pm 0.5	<0.01

WMT: Hand to Box	CP	2.6 ± 0.6	2.7 ± 0.5	3.5 ± 0.5	<0.01
	CP + KT	2.2 ± 0.6	2.5 ± 0.7	3.2 ± 0.7	<0.01

Note: CP = Conventional Physiotherapy; KT = Kinesio Taping; ROM = Range of Motion; MAS = Modified Ashworth Scale; WMT = Wolf Motor Function Test. Only select measures are shown for brevity.

Between-Group Analysis

The Mann-Whitney U test was used to compare outcomes directly between the two groups at each assessment point (Table 4).

There were no statistically significant differences between the CP and CP+KT groups for any of the four ROM parameters or the six WMT functional tasks at any assessment point (all $p > 0.05$).

In stark contrast, the between-group analysis of MAS scores revealed statistically significant differences at all three time points. The CP+KT group demonstrated significantly lower spasticity (lower MAS scores) than the CP group alone at the 1st assessment ($p = 0.04$), and this difference became more pronounced at the 2nd ($p = 0.002$) and 3rd ($p < 0.001$) assessments.

Table 4: Between-Group Comparisons (Mann-Whitney U Test)

Outcome Measure	Assessment	Mean Rank (CP)	Mean Rank (CP+KT)	p-value
ROM: Forearm Flexion	1st	18.50	18.50	1.00
	2nd	17.86	19.14	0.70
	3rd	17.08	19.92	0.40
MAS Score	1st	21.40	15.50	0.04
	2nd	23.80	13.10	0.002
	3rd	25.60	11.30	<0.001
WMT: Hand to Table	1st	18.90	18.00	0.54
	2nd	17.50	19.40	0.49
	3rd	17.30	19.60	0.68

Note: Statistically significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are in bold. CP = Conventional Physiotherapy; KT = Kinesio Taping.

In summary, while both interventions led to significant improvements in ROM and functional task performance over time, the addition of Kinesio Taping to conventional physiotherapy resulted in a statistically superior reduction of upper limb spasticity in patients with subacute stroke.

Discussion

This study aimed to evaluate the additive effects of KT combined with CP on upper limb recovery in subacute stroke patients, specifically measuring ROM, spasticity, and functional motor performance. The key finding of this RCT is that while both intervention groups demonstrated statistically significant

improvements in all measured outcomes over the six weeks, the between-group analysis revealed a negligible result. The combination of CP and KT led to a statistically significant reduction in upper limb spasticity, as measured by the Modified Ashworth Scale (MAS), compared to CP alone. This was evident at the first assessment and became increasingly pronounced at subsequent follow-ups. In contrast, the improvements in ROM and functional task performance, though clinically notable and favouring the KT group in final mean scores, did not reach statistical significance between the groups.

The significant reduction in spasticity observed in the KT group aligns with the findings of several previous studies. For example, Ozden et al. (16) reported that KT application improved ROM, reduced spasticity, and enhanced motor function, attributing these benefits to KT's proposed mechanisms of reducing pain and stiffness, improving proprioception, and facilitating better muscle function. This consistency across studies strengthens the evidence for KT's role in managing post-stroke hypertonia. The results of Naviwala et al. (17) and Lee et al. (18), who found significant improvements in upper extremity motor function, coordination, and strength with KT, further supported the potential of this adjunctive modality. The mechanism is thought to involve enhanced sensory input and proprioceptive feedback from the tape, which may modulate neural excitability at the spinal level, leading to a reduction in spasticity.

However, the absence of a statistically significant between-group difference in ROM and functional outcomes (WMT) presented a more complex picture. This result is, in fact, consistent with a body of literature that has failed to find a clear functional superiority for KT over conventional care. Our findings echo those of Fandim et al. (12), who found that KT did not produce a discernible difference in upper limb function or ROM compared to conventional therapy alone, despite noting a significant decrease in spasticity. This suggests that while KT may effectively address the neuromuscular component of spasticity, this reduction does not automatically translate into immediate, measurable gains in complex functional tasks within a short intervention period. This dichotomy is further supported by Wang et al. (19) who reported no significant differences in Fugl-Meyer scores or Barthel index values between KT and control groups, indicating that KT's benefits may be specific to certain

impairment-level outcomes rather than overall activity or participation levels.

The contrast between the current study's spasticity results and the functional results highlighted a critical point in stroke rehabilitation: an improvement at the impairment level (e.g., reduced spasticity) is a positive outcome but does not always directly equate to functional recovery, which is influenced by a multitude of other factors such as strength, coordination, learnt non-use, and cognitive function. This may explain why a study like Hassan et al. (20), which focused specifically on spasticity management, found significant functional differences by the fourth week, while our study and others with a broader focus did not.

Conclusion:

This study demonstrated that while both conventional physiotherapy and Kinesio Taping (KT) combined with physiotherapy led to significant improvements in upper limb function, range of motion (ROM), and spasticity in post-stroke patients, KT showed a significantly greater reduction in spasticity. However, no statistically significant differences were observed between groups in ROM or functional task performance (WMT). Still, the findings suggest that Kinesio taping offers a significant advantage in managing spasticity, making it a useful adjunctive treatment in the rehabilitation of patients with subacute stroke, even though it might not enhance improvements in range of motion or functional outcomes above those attained with traditional therapy, yet it can be added as a potential adjunct for beneficial effects.

Limitations And Recommendations:

The study faced challenges like consistent patient compliance over the six-week intervention, a lack of post-intervention follow-up, and limited insights into the long-term sustainability of improvements in function, ROM, and spasticity. Future studies should use larger, more diverse samples and incorporate objective tools (e.g., biomarkers, neuroimaging, biomechanics) to enhance accuracy and generalizability. Also, comparative research with other adjunct therapies (e.g., electrical stimulation, robotics, virtual reality) is recommended for a better understanding of KT's unique or synergistic role in stroke rehabilitation.

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